

THE INVERTASE ACTIVITY OF YEAST IN PRESENCE OF ACIDS AND SALTS

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Invertase activity of brewer's yeast has been found to maintain a practically constant level in presence of constituent ions of different acids at the optimum pH (4.5). Activity of yeast invertase, purified by dialysis and precipitation with alcohol at the optimum pH , is appreciably influenced by different salts at the same pH (4.5).

Influence of hydrogen-ion concentration on the activity of invertase has been thoroughly studied by different investigators. Euler and Laurin (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1919, 108, 63) found yeast saccharase most stable near its optimum pH (4.5). The method of purification of enzymes, originally developed by Willstätter and his co-workers is based on the elution of adsorbed enzymes on suitable adsorbents by changing the hydrogen-ion concentration (vide Kraut, "Methoden der Adsorption und Elution", 1928). Experiments on adsorption of enzymes by suitable adsorbents have revealed in most cases the influence of ions on the binding capacity of the adsorbents. Adsorbed enzymes, again, may be easily liberated in the free state under the influence of a suitable ionic environment. Thus, invertase was easily removed from its adsorbent alumina with a trivalent anion such as a phosphate or an arsenate. No systematic adsorption experiments, however, have been carried out to study the influence of ions on the enzymes and their activity inspite of the recent practice of isolating invertase in the chemically pure state by the use of suitable adsorbents. Adams and Hudson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1359) have been able to prepare invertase in a highly pure active state from yeast with bentonite as the adsorbent. As adsorption experiments are greatly influenced by the presence of ions, a systematic work on these lines appears to be necessary. The object of the present paper is to study the influence of different ions on the enzyme activity of yeast invertase, purified under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried brewer's yeast powder (100 g.) was mixed with water (150 c.c.) to form a paste. The paste was treated with toluol (20 c.c.) and stirred at 30° with a rod for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to a thin sludge. The yeast was autolysed at this stage and the autolysed mixture was diluted with water (200 c.c.) at 30° and kept for 1 hour. Toluol (4 c.c.) was again added and the mixture was filtered with Kieselguhr under suction. The filtrate was used for each experiment (14 c.c. of the filtrate $\equiv$ 10 g. of dried yeast powder). The substrate was 80 g. sucrose in 200 c.c. water. In the first case (Table Ia) $N/10$ solutions of hydrochloric, sulphuric, citric, oxalic and acetic acids were used to adjust pH of the enzyme-substrate mixture to 4.5 (optimum value). Invertase activity was tested with Benedict's quantitative reagent. An aliquot portion of the digestion mixture was titrated with standard Benedict's reagent and the total amount of glucose formed by the invertase

of 10 g. yeast powder was calculated. In the second place (Table IIA), experiments were made with $N/10$ solutions of potassium chloride, sodium chloride, sodium sulphate, potassium sulphate, calcium chloride, barium chloride, aluminium chloride and potassium ferrocyanide on adjustment of p_H of the enzyme-substrate mixture to 4.5 with $N/10$ solution of acetic acid.

A parallel series of experiments was conducted with yeast invertase, purified by precipitation of the dialysed extract from crude yeast with 50% alcohol, at p_H 4.5. The activity of this enzyme was found to be of a higher order than that observed before hand. The results have been incorporated in Tables IB and IIB. Glass electrodes were used for determination of H-ion concentration or activity with a Leeds Northrup p_H -meter.

Tables IA and IIA refer to invertase extract of 10 g. yeast with substrate of 80 g. saccharose in 200 c.c. water + 2 c.c. toluol and $N/10$ acids. Tables IB and IIB refer to alcohol-purified invertase solution (29 c.c. $\equiv$ 10 g. yeast) with substrate of 80 g. of saccharose in 200 c.c. water + $N/10$ acids at p_H 4.5

TABLE I

Acid solution used to adjust p_H to 4.5.	A. Invertase activity (g. glucose formed by 10 g. of yeast extract).	B. Invertase activity of extract corresponding to 10 g. yeast.
HCl	0.406	4.08
H ₂ SO ₄	0.403	4.4
Citric acid	0.406	2.5
Oxalic acid	0.403	2.3
Acetic acid	0.403	2.3

TABLE II

Vol. of $N/10$ soln. used = 10 c.c.

Electrolytes.	A. Invertase activity (g. glucose formed by 10 g. yeast extract).	B. Invertase activity of extract corresponding to 10 g. yeast.
KCl	0.385	3.4
NaCl	0.385	3.2
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.379	2.2
K ₂ SO ₄	0.379	3.3
CaCl ₂	0.391	2.6
BaCl ₂	0.391	2.2
AlCl ₃	0.419	3.9
K ₄ Fe (CN) ₆	0.419	3.1

DISCUSSION

Table I (A and B) demonstrates the influence of ions on the invertase activity of yeast. In the first place it is evident that p_H is the principal determining factor in influencing the invertase activity; the anions, having little effect so far as the invertase extract, not treated with alcohol, is concerned. But in the case of the alcohol extract (vide Table IB), the activity appears to depend on the nature of the anions. Usually the organic anions depress the activity markedly.

Table II represents results on the study of the influence of the electrolytes, the p_H being adjusted to 4.5 with $N/10$ acetic acid. From Table III it appears that provided the p_H remains constant, the invertase activity is not seriously affected by salts in cases where no alcohol is used. But Table IIB shows greater variations, $AlCl_3$ having the highest activity while $BaCl_2$ has the least value. Whether this change in activity is to be attributed to adsorption of ions is a matter requiring a thorough study.

As observed by Adams and Hudson (*loc. cit.*), their invertase preparations consisted chiefly of protein although they still contained only a small amount of carbohydrate. Accordingly, the invertase activity of the enzyme-substrate mixture will generally be controlled by biologically active proteins of which the enzymes are composed. The author (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1936, 24, 363) observed specific adsorption of H^+ ions from oxalic acid by diphtheria antibody globulin. It has also been proved by the author (*ibid.*, 1938, 26, 469) that normal globulin possesses a stronger affinity for H^+ ions than the antibody globulin. Ordinary proteins of the system become sensitized on immunisation and accordingly their ionic adsorption properties also change.

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